

Metadata Template

Title of dataset	<i>A Carbon Source in a Carbon Sink: Carbon Dioxide and Methane Dynamics in Open-Water Peatland Pools</i>
Keywords	
Lead author for the dataset	<i>Pierre Taillardat</i>
Title and position of lead author	<i>Senior Research Fellow</i>
Organization and address of lead author	<i>Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada Current addresses: National University of Singapore</i>
Email address of lead author	<i>Taillardat.pierre@nus.edu.sg</i>
Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	<i>Annika Linkhorst, Charles P. Deblois, Antonin Prijac, Laure Gandois, Alain Tremblay, Michelle Garneau</i>
Organization associated with the data	<i>Same as for lead author</i>
Funding	<i>This research was funded by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada and Hydro-Quebec to Michelle Garneau (RDCPJ 514218-17).</i>
License	<i>CCBY</i>
Geographic location – verbal description	<i>The data was collected in a boreal peatland in Minganie, Québec, Canada (50°31'N; 63°12'W, elevation: 108 ± 5 m asl).</i>
Time frame - Begin date	<i>01/06/2019 (MM/DD/YYYY)</i>
Time frame - End date	<i>10/10/2020 (MM/DD/YYYY)</i>
General study design	<i>This study was led by Michelle Garneau's lab in collaboration with researchers from other institutions in Quebec and France. In total, the study site was visited monthly and automated continuous equipment were left on the site between visits.</i>
Methods description	<i>Please refer to the manuscript for full description of the methods used.</i>
Quality control	<i>All data were carefully checked by at least two coauthors.</i>

Figure2_Figure6.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
SiteID	Sampling location (5 open water pools)	M## (goes from pool M11 to M15)	NA
Year	Sampling year	-	
Month	Sampling month	In letters	NA
Sampling_date	Sampling date	dd/mm/YYYY	NA

Sampling_time	Sampling time	HH:MM	NA
Pool_size_m2	Surface area of the pool	Square meter	NA
CO2atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
CH4atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
AtmP_Pa	Atmospheric pressure	Pascal	NA
air_pressure_atm	Atmospheric pressure	Atmosphere	NA
Windspeed_msec	Wind Speed	Meter per second	NA
pCH4_ppm	Stream dissolved CH ₄ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
pCO2_ppm	Stream dissolved CO ₂ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
d13CCH4_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	NA
d13CCO2_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	NA
FluxCO2_mgCm2d	CO ₂ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FluxCH4_mgCm2d	CH ₄ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
Water.body	Water body type (M=Pool; PW= porewater; W=well)	-	
T_degC	Water temperature	Degrees Celsius	NA
pH	pH	-	NA
water_temp_K	Water temperature	Kelvin	NA
pH	Water pH	NA	NA
DOC_mgL	Dissolved organic carbon concentration	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
Sol_CO2	Coefficient solubility of carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	NA	NA
Sol_CH4	Coefficient solubility of methane	NA	NA
water_pCO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_pCH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA

water_CO2_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
water_CH4_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
air_CO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
air_CH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
deltaCO2_umolL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Micromole per liter	NA
deltaCH4_umolL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Micromole per liter	NA
deltaCO2_mgCL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
deltaCH4_mgCL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CO2_mgCL	Carbon dioxide concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CH4_mgCL	Methane concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CO2CH4_mgCL	Carbon dioxide to methane ratio	-	
k_CO2_measured_md	Gas transfer velocities of CO ₂	Meter per day	NA
k_CH4_measured_md	Gas transfer velocities of CH ₄	Meter per day	NA
Sc_CO2	Schmidt number of a CO ₂ based on field temperature	NA	NA
Sc_CH4	Schmidt number of a CH ₄ based on field temperature	NA	NA
k600_CO2_measured_md	Normalized gas transfer velocities of CO ₂ (k at 20°C in freshwater at a Schmidt number of 600)	Meter per day	NA
k600_CH4_measured_md	Normalized gas transfer velocities of CH ₄ (k at 20°C in freshwater at a Schmidt number of 600)	Meter per day	NA

Figure3_Figure4ab.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-

CO2_ppm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ at the outlet station (#8)	Part per million	Blank
CH4_ppm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ at the outlet station (#8)	Part per million	Blank
Temp_degC	Water temperature	Degrees Celsius	Blank
CO2atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
CH4atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
windspeed_msec1	Wind Speed	Meter per second	NA
Rain_mm_Tot	Cumulative rain	mm	NA
AirTemp_degC	Air temperature	Degrees Celsius	Blank
WTD_m	Water table depth	m	NA
Temp5cm_degC	Soil Temperature at -5cm	degC	NA
Temp10cm_degC	Soil Temperature at -10cm	degC	NA
Temp20cm_degC	Soil Temperature at -20cm	degC	NA
Temp40cm_degC	Soil Temperature at -40cm	degC	NA
PoolT_degC	Pool Temperature	degC	NA
Sol_CO2	Coefficient solubility of carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	NA	NA
Sol_CH4	Coefficient solubility of methane	NA	NA
air_pressure_atm	Air pressure	Atmosphere	NA
water_pCO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_pCH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_pCO2_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
water_pCH4_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
air_CO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
air_CH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
deltaCO2_umolL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Micromole per liter	NA
deltaCH4_umolL1	Concentration difference between air and water	Micromole per liter	NA
CO2_mgCL	Carbon dioxide concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CH4_ugCL	Methane concentration in water	Microgram of carbon per liter	NA

Figure4cd.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Fulldate	Sampling date and time	dd/mm/YYYY HH:MM	
water_pCO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_pCH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_temp_K	Water temperature	Kelvin	NA
Sol_CO2	Coefficient solubility of carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	NA	NA
Sol_CH4	Coefficient solubility of methane	NA	NA
air_pressure_atm	Atmospheric pressure	Atmosphere	NA
water_CO2_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
water_CH4_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
pool_CO2_daily_median_umolL1	Daily median concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
pool_CH4_daily_median_umolL1	Daily median concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
pool_CO2_var_umolL1	Variation between sample and daily median concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
pool_CH4_var_umolL1	Variation between sample and daily median concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
pool_CO2_var_mgCL	Variation between sample and daily median concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
pool_CH4_var_ugCL	Variation between sample and daily median concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA

Figure4ef.csv

	Description	Unit or	Empty value code
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		code explanation or date format	
SiteID	Sampling location (5 open water pools)	M## (goes from pool M11 to M15)	NA
Year	Sampling year	-	
Month	Sampling month	In letters	NA
Sampling_date	Sampling date	dd/mm/YYYY	NA
Sampling_time	Sampling time	HH:MM	NA
TimeDate	Sampling date and time	dd/mm/YYYY HH:MM	
CO2atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
CH4atm_ppm	Atmospheric CO ₂ partial pressure (from eddy covariance tower)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
AtmP_Pa	Atmospheric pressure	Pascal	NA
air_pressure_atm	Atmospheric pressure	Atmosphere	NA
Windspeed_msec	Wind Speed	Meter per second	NA
pCH4_ppm	Stream dissolved CH ₄ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
pCO2_ppm	Stream dissolved CO ₂ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	NA
d13CCH4_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH ₄ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	NA
d13CCO2_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CO ₂ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	NA
Water.body	Water body type (M=Pool; PW= porewater; W=well)	-	
T_degC	Water temperature	Degrees Celsius	NA
pH	pH	-	NA
DOC_mgL	Dissolved organic carbon concentration	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
Sol_CO2	Coefficient solubility of carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	NA	NA
Sol_CH4	Coefficient solubility of methane	NA	NA
water_pCO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA
water_pCH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in water	Micro atmosphere	NA

water_CO2_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CO ₂ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
water_CH4_umolL1	Concentration of dissolved CH ₄ in water	Micromole per liter	NA
air_CO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
air_CH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in the air	Micro atmosphere	NA
CO2_mgCL	Carbon dioxide concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CH4_mgCL	Methane concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA

Figure5_daily.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date	Measurement date	dd-mm-yy	-
Flux_mgCm2d	Carbon dioxide emission to the atmosphere	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
Flux_type	CO2 evasion, CH4 evasion or CH4 ebullition	NA	NA

LiteratureReview_OpenWaterPeatlandPools.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Reference	Publication reference	-	NA
Year of publication	Publication year of publication	-	NA
Site.ID	Study site ID	-	NA
Country	Study site Country	-	NA
Latitude	Study site latitude	-	NA
Longitude	Study site longitude	-	NA
Sampling.date.and.frequency	Sampling date and frequency	-	NA
Pool_Depth_m	Pool depth	-	NA
Pool_surface_m2	Pool surface area	-	NA
Pool_occupation_catchment_%	Total occupation of the pool(s) within the catchment	-	NA
Peat_occupation_catchment_%	Total occupation of the peatland(s) within the catchment	-	NA

Pool_type	Pool type (beaver pond, peatland pool bog, peatland pool fen, thaw pool, wetland pond)	-	NA
Catchment_land_cover	Catchment land cover	-	NA
Permafrost	Indication of permafrost in the study site (continuous, discontinuous, sporadic, no)	-	NA
DOC_range	Dissolved Organic Carbon concentration range	-	NA
DOC_mean	Dissolved Organic Carbon mean concentration	-	NA
DOC_median	Dissolved Organic Carbon median concentration	-	NA
DOC_unit	Dissolved Organic Carbon concentration unit	-	NA
CH4_range	Dissolved methane concentration range	-	NA
CH4_mean	Dissolved methane mean concentration	-	NA
CH4_median	Dissolved methane median concentration	-	NA
CH4_unit	Dissolved methane concentration unit	-	NA
CO2_range	Dissolved carbon dioxide concentration range	-	NA
CO2_mean	Dissolved carbon dioxide mean concentration	-	NA
CO2_median	Dissolved carbon dioxide median concentration	-	NA
CO2_unit	Dissolved carbon dioxide concentration unit	-	NA
FCO2_range	Carbon dioxide diffusion range	-	NA
FCO2_mean	Carbon dioxide mean diffusion	-	NA
FCO2_median	Carbon dioxide median diffusion	-	NA
FCO2_unit	Carbon dioxide diffusion unit	-	NA
diffusive_FCH4_range	Methane diffusion range	-	NA
diffusive_FCH4_mean	Methane mean diffusion	-	NA
diffusive_FCH4_median	Methane median diffusion	-	NA
FCH4_unit	Methane diffusion unit	-	NA
CH4_ebullition	Methane ebullition	-	NA
CH4_ebullition_unit	Methane mean ebullition	-	NA
k600_CO2	Normalized gas transfer velocities of CO ₂ (k at 20°C in	-	NA

	freshwater at a Schmidt number of 600)		
k600_CO2_unit	Unit of normalized gas transfer velocities of CO ₂	-	NA
k600_CH4	Normalized gas transfer velocities of CH ₄ (k at 20°C in freshwater at a Schmidt number of 600)	-	NA
k600_CH4_unit	Unit of normalized gas transfer velocities of CH ₄	-	NA
doi	Publication DOI	-	NA
Comments	Any comment	-	NA
CH4_mean_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved methane mean concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
CH4_median_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved methane median concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
CO2_mean_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide mean concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
CO2_median_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide median concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
FCO2_mean_gCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide mean diffusion	Gram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCO2_median_gCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide median diffusion	Gram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCH4_diffusion_mean_gCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved methane mean diffusion	Gram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCH4_diffusion_median_gCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved methane median diffusion	Gram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCH4_ebullition_mean_gCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved methane ebullition	Gram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
DOC_mean_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved organic carbon mean concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
DOC_median_mgCL	Homogeneized dissolved organic carbon median concentration	Milligran carbon per liter	NA
FCO2_mean_mgCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide mean diffusion	Milligram of carbon per	NA

		square meter per day	
FCO2_median_mgCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved carbon dioxide median diffusion	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCH4_diffusion_mean_mgCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved methane mean diffusion	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA
FCH4_diffusion_median_mgCm2d	Homogeneized dissolved methane median diffusion	Miligram of carbon per square meter per day	NA

Figure9ab_.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Reference	Publication reference	-	NA
Category			
Site ID	Study site ID	-	NA
Location	Study site Country	-	NA
Latitude	Study site latitude	-	NA
Longitude	Study site longitude	-	NA
Sampling_date	Sampling date	-	NA
area_ha	Water body surface area	Hectare	NA
area_km2	Water body surface area	Square kilometer	
CO2_umoll1	Carbon dioxide concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CH4_umoll1	Methane concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CO2_mgCL	Carbon dioxide concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA
CH4_mgCL	Methane concentration in water	Milligram of carbon per liter	NA

Figure9c_.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
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total_CH4_flux_mgCH4m-2d-1	Total methane emission	Milligram of methane per square meter per day	NA
total_CH4_flux_mgCm-2d-1	Total methane emission	Milligram of carbon per square meter per day	
WaterBody	Water body type	-	NA
Ref	Study site reference	-	NA
Source	Metadata source (Rosentreter et al. 2021 or This Study)	-	NA